

Studies on Synthesis of 2-[3'-(4''-Acetylaminophenyl)-2'-aryl-4'-thiazolidinon-5'-yl-methyl]-4,5-dihydroimidazoles

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Condensation of ethylenediamine with 2-aryl-3-(4'-acetamidophenyl)-5-carboxymethyl-4-thiazolidinones gave 2-[3'-(4''-acetylaminophenyl)-2'-aryl-4'-thiazolidinon-5'-yl-methyl]-4,5-dihydroimidazoles. Their antimicrobial activity have been studied.

2-IMIDAZOLINE derivative possess various physiological and antimicrobial activities¹. Although several derivatives of 4-thiazolidinones having versatile pharmacological and industrial values have been reported, some of the substituted-thiazolidinones have been found to possess diverse biological activities². 4-Aminoacetanilide and their derivatives find varied uses³.

In order to incorporate pharmacological properties of imidazoles, 4-thiazolidinone and 4-aminoacetanilide, we have prepared some 4,5-dihydroimidazole derivatives containing thiazolidinone ring and aminoacetanilide moiety. The synthesis involves preparation of anils from 4-aminoacetanilide and different substituted aromatic aldehydes in alcohol followed by its cyclisation to 4-thiazolidinone derivative using mercaptosuccinic acid. 4-Thiazolidinone derivatives are treated with ethylenediamine to obtain imidazole ring (Scheme 1).

Scheme 1

Experimental

The purity of the compounds was checked by tlc. Melting points were determined in open capillary and are uncorrected. The ir spectra (KBr) of the compounds were recorded on a Beckmann IR-20 spectrophotometer. The structure of the compounds were established on the basis of their elemental analysis, counter synthesis⁴, mixed melting points and infrared spectra.

N-Substituted-benzal-4-acetylaminobenzaldehyde : Substituted-benzaldehyde (0.02 mol) was added to 4-aminoacetanilide (0.02 mol, 3 g) in ethanol (95% ; 30 ml). The contents were refluxed for 3 h on a water-bath. The excess of solvent was then distilled off, and the resulting solid was filtered, washed with water, dried and recrystallised from 95% ethanol.

2-Aryl-3-(4'-acetamidophenyl)-5-carboxymethyl-4-thiazolidinone : A mixture of N-substituted-benzal-4-acetylaminobenzaldehyde (0.01 mol), thiomalic acid (0.015 mol, 2.25 g) and anhydrous zinc chloride (0.5 g) was heated for 2 h at 160°, and then at 180° for 30 min. It was then treated with a solution of NaHCO₃ (4 N) and filtered. The resulting solid was reprecipitated with dilute HCl, filtered, dried and recrystallised from 95% ethanol.

2-[3'-(4''-Acetylaminophenyl)-2'-aryl-4'-thiazolidinone-5'-yl-methyl]-4,5-dihydroimidazole : A mixture of 2-aryl-3-(4'-acetamidophenyl)-5-carboxymethyl-4-thiazolidinone (0.01 mol) and ethylenediamine (3 ml) was refluxed on a steam-bath for 4 h. The contents were then cooled and poured into ice-water. The resulting solid was filtered, washed with water, dried and recrystallised with 95% ethanol (Table 1).

Spectral study : Ir spectra of the compounds (1) showed characteristic bands at 1 665, 1 600 and 1 650 cm⁻¹ for C=O stretching frequency of 4-thiazolidinone ring system. A sharp band at 1 640 (C=N) and a band at 2 900 cm⁻¹ (CH₂ group of imidazole ring system) were obtained. Uv absorption maxima was obtained at 304.5 nm.

Biological activity : The imidazole derivatives were tested for antibacterial activity by cup-plate method⁵ using gram-positive bacteria *S. aureus* and

TABLE 1—PHYSICAL DATA OF THE IMIDAZOLES*

Sl. no.	R	Mol. formula	M.p.** °C	Yield %
1.	H	C ₂₁ H ₂₂ N ₄ O ₂ S	204	51
2.	2.OH	C ₂₁ H ₂₂ N ₄ O ₃ S	308	49
3.	4.OH	C ₂₁ H ₂₂ N ₄ O ₃ S	298	49
4.	5.Br.2.OH	C ₂₁ H ₂₁ BrN ₄ O ₃ S	385d	45
5.	4 Cl	C ₂₁ H ₂₁ Cl ₂ N ₄ O ₃ S	254	47
6.	3.NO ₂	C ₂₁ H ₂₁ N ₅ O ₄ S	340d	43
7.	4.NO ₂	C ₂₁ H ₂₁ N ₅ O ₄ S	168	45
8.	4.OH.3.OOH ₂	C ₂₃ H ₂₄ N ₄ O ₄ S	166	61
9.	5.Br.4.OH.3.OCH ₃	C ₂₃ H ₂₃ BrN ₄ O ₄ S	267	46
10.	4.OH.5 I.3.OCH ₃	C ₂₃ H ₂₃ IN ₄ O ₄ S	236	48
11.	4 OCH ₃	C ₂₃ H ₂₄ N ₄ O ₄ S	237	47
12.	3,4(OCH ₃) ₂	C ₂₃ H ₂₄ N ₄ O ₄ S	181	53
13.	5.Br.3,4(OCH ₃) ₂	C ₂₃ H ₂₃ BrN ₄ O ₄ S	253	51
14.	3,4(OCH ₃) ₂	C ₂₃ H ₂₃ N ₄ O ₄ S	293	53

*All compounds gave satisfactory N and S analyses. ** (d) = Decomposed.

gram-negative bacteria *E. coli*. The testing was carried out in 1 : 4 dioxan solution at a concentration of 10 µg ml⁻¹.

In vitro antitubercular activity of the imidazole derivatives was studied against H₃₇R_v strain of *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* in Lowenstein-Jensen egg media at 0.02 µg ml⁻¹. The retardation of growth was studied up to 6 weeks at 37°.

The results of antibacterial screening showed that only compounds having 2-hydroxy and 4-hydroxy substitutions to phenyl ring are active (inhibition zone ≤ 20 mm) against *E. coli*. The compounds with 4-hydroxy, 5-bromo-2-hydroxy, 4-chloro, 4-hydroxy-3-methoxy, 5-bromo-4-hydroxy-3-methoxy, 3,4-dimethoxy and 5-bromo-3,4-dimethoxy substitution to phenyl ring showed good activity against *S. aureus*; all exhibiting inhibition zone diameter ≤ 20 mm, except the 5-bromo-2-hydroxy substitution (> 20 mm).

From the antitubercular activity data, very few compounds, i.e. 4-methoxy, 4-chloro, 5-bromo-2-hydroxy and 4-hydroxy-3-methoxy substituted phenyl derivatives showed activity against H₃₇R_v strain of *M. tuberculosis*.

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